

Embracing Dewantara's Values For Global Student-Centered Learning Approach: Equity In Learning And Community-Practice Necessity - A Scoping Review From A Hierarchical And Collectivistic Cultural Context

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 23, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: July 24, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Student-Centered Learning, Equity Learning, Collaborative Learning, Contextual Learning, Reflective Practice, Professionalism</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8179133</p>	<p><i>Student-centered learning (SCL) is a global approach in medical education, in which learning is centered around students' needs. Nevertheless, countries that hold hierarchical and collectivistic culture, such as Indonesia, may face setbacks in implementing the SCL, for they have to first overcome lack of teacher-student dialogue. Exceptionally, an Indonesian educational figure born in this cultural background in the early 1900s, Dewantara, has set an educational pillar of 'Tut Wuri Handayani' (TWH) / 'let the students lead' in his period. In this study, we investigate Dewantara's values embracing the recent international evidence in SCL in health professions education (HPE) to demonstrate that people in this cultural context also necessitate equity in learning.</i></p> <p>Methods</p> <p><i>A scoping review was used to reveal the alignment of the Indonesian educational local wisdom with SCL's global perspective. We searched the articles based on Dewantara's keywords of 'equity,' 'collaborative-contextual', and 'reflective learning' or 'professionalism' through advanced search engines for articles between 2010-2020. We used the context of HPE as the authors' basis of knowledge. We found 118 articles and analyzed them using PRISMA methods.</i></p> <p>Results</p> <p><i>Twenty eight articles grouped into specific themes based on Dewantara's values. The articles were found around the globe representing the validated values.</i></p> <p>Conclusions</p> <p><i>Despite Dewantara's existence exposure to a hierarchical culture, he articulated the need for partnership learning, which largely aligns with the current global trend of SCL in education. Likewise, he made the most of the collectivistic culture to nurture lifetime peer-support community of practice that could benefit for future SCL.</i></p>

Introduction

Current global education paradigm, including that in medical education, is shifting into student-centered learning (SCL) (Harden & Liley, 2018). Over the course of medical and health professions education history, the dominant learning program largely resembled a teacher-centered learning, frequently called traditional teaching methods, whereby the teaching is largely one-directional. Since mid-1900s, countless studies have been done to gauge teaching delivery effectiveness, and evidence showed that the way knowledge is perceived and retrieved depends more on the students' ability to accept, receive, analyze, use, and construct meaning of all learning experiences. Student-centered learning principles were pioneered by many of socio-constructivism theorists as Hayward in 1905, John Dewey in 1950s (the pragmatism theory), Piaget (developmental learning), and Malcolm Knowles (self-directed learning) as explained by O'Neill & Mc Mahon (2005) and Bronowski (2010).

SCL rests on these critical components: active learning, deep learning, students' responsibility and authority in the learning process, equal interdependence, mutual respect between teacher-student, student-peer learning, and reflective approaches to the teaching and learning process (Bronowski, 2010; Wright, 2011). A study revealed that SCL promises a more efficacious strategy in education to transform the students to future champions of supportive changes (Niklen et al., 2016). Thus, SCL brings influences to the educational process. More active

teaching methods were developed, starting with problem-based learning and growing worldwide eventually (Albanese, 2000; Dolmans, et al., 2015).

Following the development of a more active strategy for facilitating learning that stands more on students' needs, teaching and learning strategies were explored to establish evidence for the student-centered learning approach. In medical education context, SCL has shifted teachers' perspective and value of instruction, which were introduced as 'roles of medical teachers' (Harden & Crosby, 2000; Harden & Liley, 2018). With regards to achieving learning goals, teachers have shifted from 'giving' or 'lecturing' into 'facilitating learning' and 'letting students lead'. As a consequence, teaching activities have become more complex and require heavy preparation to invite more students' participation (Albanese, 2000; Dolmans, et al., 2015).

However, despite the fact that SCL concept is a worldwide recommendation in today's education, many teachers find it challenging to apply into their teaching and learning process, mainly because it has complex instructions (Keiler, 2018). Consequently, there should be continuous faculty development program to support teachers in facilitating learning, giving feedback, and stimulating reflection. Facilitating student-centered learning should also be carefully tailored to fit the cultural context of the teachers and students. The culturally contextual education is especially important in countries that exhibit wide power-distance/ hierarchical culture such as those in Asia, whereby student-teacher dialogue is rare, and learning is mainly teacher-centered (Soemantri et al., 2022; Findyartini et al., 2023). Nevertheless, wide power-distance culture is also found in Africa, Mediterranean, and South American cultures, as explained by a theory of 'cultural dimensions' by Hofstede (2011) that has been studied in many countries for business-related matters.

Indonesia, with its vastly diverse ethnic groups and language, is a prime example of a country with a wide power distance gap. In medical and health professions education in Indonesia, the hierarchical social gap has impacted the patient-centered and student-centered learning implementation (Claramita et al., 2013; Suhoyo et al., 2017). The sociocultural hierarchy limits the dialogue between the doctor-patient, teacher-student, and presumably employers-employees, and understandably, parents-children. As such, instead of 'guiding' and 'empowering', the perceived higher hierarchy talks more, acts more, and the perceived lower hierarchy should follow (Claramita et al., 2020).

Despite its current conditions, Indonesia had a remarkable history of supporting SCL principles. This momentum was brought about by Ki Hadjar Dewantara, the nation's first father of national education. In 1920, he introduced the concept of *Tut Wuri* ('following students' or 'let the students lead') *Handayani* (by 'empowering' them), which can be interpreted as 'let the student lead to achieve their utmost potential' (Tauchid, et al., 1962; Claramita, et al., 2020). Few international publications have studied Dewantara's educational pillars and its subsequent implementation in a series of Taman Siswa schools in Indonesia (McVey, 1967; Hings, 1975; Tsuchiya, 1978; and recently, Koe., 2020; Hanson et al., 2021). Those studies explored the life and schools of Dewantara, but not specifically about the relationship between his educational concepts and modern-day SCL. The community of practice settled by Dewantara and those schools, from kindergarten, elementary, high schools, up to the university level, paid respect to Montessori's and Froebel's educational principles, namely in putting students as the centre of learning (Tauchid et al., 1962). Therefore, to prove that Dewantara's local principles follow the current global principle of SCL approach, we need more evidence to support the notion.

A literature study on Dewantara's educational pillars, which was validated by masters students in medical and health professions education, confirmed the educational values as: (1) equity between learners and teachers regardless of the strong hierarchical social culture, to optimize students' participation in learning, (2) utilization of cultural events or instruments as rigorous learning resources to enhance the sensory abilities and social sensitivity of the students towards community's needs by learning collaboratively, (3) encouraging observation-based learning to promote self-directed learning by helping the students to reflect on their mistakes, to be independent thinkers and to be responsible persons, to minimize gaps between attitudes and behaviors, and (4) to provide role models and opportunities for students to participate in learning (Claramita, 2016). Accordingly, our current study aims to demonstrate that Dewantara's educational pillars, despite (being in the 1920 backdrop) and (the fact that the country has a wide power-distance culture), align with the latest evidence of SCL, in medical and health professions education context. It is highly important to demonstrate that in a country with a wide-power distance culture like Indonesia, a more partnership relationship between people was well-articulated by an educational leader, who successfully developed an educational community-practice, a century ago. Also, it is possible that the evidence presented in this study can be of support and inspiration to other countries with similar power-distance culture, as found in Hofstede's study (2011), to apply SCL principles in their respective education journey and appropriate cultural context. To approach a more interactive and

dynamic learning process is human nature and is a worldwide plea. To validate this purpose, we need to conduct a scoping review. Table 1 presents the proposition of Dewantara’s educational values to the global SCL principles.

Table 1 The proposition of Dewantara’s educational values compared to the global SCL principles

Dewantara’s local articles	Educational value compilation	
	TWH (Claramita, 2016)	SCL (Bronowski, 2010)
‘Equity’	Equity between learners and teachers regardless the strong hierarchical social culture	Interdependence between teachers and learner Mutual respect within the learner and teacher relationship
‘Cultural awareness’	The best usage of cultural events or instruments as rigorous learning resources to enhance the sensory abilities and social sensitivity of the students toward community’s needs	Emphasis on deep learning and understanding Reliance on active than passive learning
‘Reflective learning’	Encouraging observation-based learning to promote self-directed learning helping the students to reflect on their mistakes	Reflective approach to the teaching and learning process. Project-based learning to put the students as the center of their learning activities
‘Professionalism’	To provide role models and opportunities for students to actively participate in learning	Increased responsibility, engagement, and accountability on the part of the students Increased sense of autonomy in the learner

Methods

Before we selected the keywords, we searched for similar key terms of student-centered approach strategy, equity, and professionalism through MeSH PubMed, as shown in Table 2. We searched using all keywords through PubMed, Science Direct, and EBSCO Host databases under the ‘medical and health professions education’ field. Start with a student-centered approach key term and continue with other keywords. Following that, we added several medical professions, such as Medic*, Nurs*, and Pharm*. We use Population, Intervention, Context, and Intervention (PICO) framework to search the articles. The PICO of these articles are as follow: 1) Population: the article come from medical and allied health professions education; 2) Intervention: the article focused on implementation of SCL strategies; 3) Context: the article comparable to keywords by Dewantara stated in Table 1; and 4) Outcome: the article shows relevant educational outcome to the SCL approach. At the end of the search process, we found 118 articles from three databases after merging all selected articles and deleting duplication. We followed the PRISMA (Page, et al., 2021) flow chart in order to extract the data.

Table 2. Search terms

Main keywords	Synonyms
Equity	Learning partnership
Student centered approach	Collaborative, contextual, project-based learning, problem-based learning, community-based learning
Professionalism	Reflective learning

Figure 1 explains the PRISMA flow process for this scoping review. The review process of 118 identified articles begins with selection based on the title’s congruence with study themes. We exclude whenever there is no full-text availability, or it is not in English. Based on the initial review process, we excluded 48 articles, and 70 eligible pieces proceeded to the next phase of quality appraisal and full-text screening.

We read the abstract and excluded the article with literature review/scoping review types in the following selection process. The eligibility criteria were original research focusing on undergraduate health professions education, and there were outcome measurements including the scope of knowledge, skills, and attitude. The selection resulted in 57 articles for further review. These full articles went into deep analysis by deep reading process, and 25 articles were excluded since they did not relate to the student-centered learning strategies or focused on different subjects or themes. Finally, we had 28 articles for final review. All those articles were given to all authors to read deeper to extract the meaning behind each article regarding TWH values. Each selection process was done through a meeting to reach an agreement, and all researchers also did the analysis. We took meaning from each article to conclude a global view on the three themes of Indonesian educational local wisdom principles.

Figure 1. Screening and filtering process of this study (PRISMA flow)

Limitations of the review

The scope of this review was firstly used title selection with keywords as explained above, about main strategies in facilitating learning towards student-centered learning approach. Studies which use strategies in facilitating learning but did not explicitly mention it in the title may not be included. For example, a study about communication skills training, which are likely to discuss about professionalism, or using one of SCL learning strategies, but did not explicitly mention one of our keywords in its title, were not included. This review is also limited to three biggest databased relevant to our keywords that was subscribed by Universitas Gadjah Mada. Studies with the same keywords in its title but outside these databased were not included.

We used the themes found in the previous study of Claramita (2016) for the values of the TWH: 'equity' or 'active participation' in learning, 'cultural and community needs awareness', 'reflective learning' or 'professionalism' to analyze the literature. When we used the theme 'professionalism' during the searching process, it raised extensive search results covering various subjects. Furthermore, professionalism is also a more specific subject for each different allied health professional. So, what we mean by 'professional' applied in teaching and learning in this study, is more to students' responsibility and authority to take an active learning process. Also, developing professionalism would need a specific strategy within each profession, which is in line with this scoping review's purpose.

Results

Twenty-eight articles were categorized into 'equity' or 'active participation', 'cultural and community needs awareness', 'reflective learning' or 'professionalism'. A series of twelve meetings (one meeting per week/two

weeks until about 4 months) were conducted by all authors to agree on article categorization before the meaning extraction for each article. For each theme, the article came from varied countries representing each global region (Northern America, Europe, Australia, Asia, and Africa). Based on the finding on thematic categorization, striving for student-centered learning, three categories of Dewantara's values as mentioned in the beginning of this paragraph were found in publications from almost all regions of the world.

Although we categorize the studies into three categories, some can fall into more than one category. For example, when a study explores the active participation of the students in the learning process, and if the setting is community services, subsequently the outcome can stimulate students' reflection on the characteristics of reflective learning and professionalism. The authors needed several meetings to decide in which category a study should be included. However, authors resolved that we did not target to differentiate the studies strictly, but more into validating the values of Dewantara that were found in those studies. Therefore, the following results and discussion under sub-headings of 'equity in learning,' 'cultural and community needs awareness,' and 'reflective learning-professionalism' also accommodate studies from different categories. Table 3 shows selected and analyzed articles in this study.

Table 3. Selected articles - analyzed.

Themes based on Dewantara's (Claramita, 2016)	Authors of the papers in this review	Content of the papers in this review	Our findings of the papers related to Dewantara's educational principles and SCL
Equity and active participation in learning	Bhayat, A., &Mahrous, M. S.(2012)	Impact of outreach activities at the college of dentistry, Taibah university.	(Equity between learner and community). The research utilized field trip/COME to increase students' sense of academic development and civic responsibility by using quantitative approach.
	Emery, N., Hund, A., Duffy, M., &Swei, A. (2019)	Students as ecologists: strategies for successful mentorship of undergraduate researchers.	(Equity in learning). This paper adds on strategy on publication mentorship (explain step by step that could improve mentee and mentor relationship) with several important notes for each step of research.
	Kreider, C. M., Medina, S., Lan, M., Wu, C., Percival, S. S., Byrd, C. E., Delislie, A., Schoenfelder, D.,&Mann, W. C. (2018)	Beyond academics: a model for simultaneously advancing campus-based supports for learning disabilities, stem students' skills for self-regulation, and mentors' knowledge for co-regulating and guiding.	(Equity in learning using participatory action). Illustrating a mentorship process in a cohort study (4-year) that is evaluated through PAR, highlighting on how to foster students' well-being - academic and career development through recognized learning developmental needs of the students with or without any disabilities in learning - indirectly, it could be assumed that the SCL is well nurtured by this system.
	Nguyen-Truong, C. K. Y., Fritz, R. L., Lee, J., Lau, C., Le, C., Kim, J., Leung, H., Nguyen, T. H., Leung, J., Le, T. V., Truong, A. M., Postma, J., Hoeksel, R., & Son, C. Van. (2018)	Interactive co-learning for research engagement and education (I-COREE) curriculum to build capacity between community partners and academic researchers.	(Equity between learner and community). This article adds on the I-COREE program that established trust and rapport with the community to develop ongoing group reflection and interactive nature of co-creation of learning activities.

Williamson, G. R., Kane, A., Plowright, H., Bunce, J., Clarke, D., & Jamison, C. (2020)	Nurse education in practice 'thinking like a nurse'changing the culture of nursing students ' clinical learning: implementing collaborative learning in practice.	(Equity between mentor and mentee). CLIPS (Collaborative Learning in Practice) was a combination strategy between PAL and COME/CBE that was implemented. The collaboration and preparedness were significant for this program. Supervision and mentoring, and role between mentor and coach were critical duringthe commencement of the program.
Hill, R., Woodward, M., & Arthur, A. (2020)	Nurse education today collaborative learning in practice (CLIP): evaluation of a new approach to clinical learning.	(The importance of equity between mentor and mentee). A service-learning program / work-place based learning adapted from the Netherlands. Supervisory relationship can be inefficientfor the students without adequate mentorship program.
Quoß, M., Rüttermann, S., & Gerhardt-szep, S. (2017)	Cross-year peer-assisted learning using the inverted ('flipped') classroom design: a pilot study in dentistry	(An effort of partnership facilitation between teacher and students). This article adds on acceptance of a ICM-cyPAL program, a combination between PAL and PBL -flipped classroom in dentistry. By the result, this program could be accepted but there was a lack of implementation of learning materials.
Ignacio, J., & Chen, H. (2020)	Nurse education today cognitive integration in health professions education: development and implementation of a collaborative learning workshop in an undergraduate nursing program.	(Equity between students and tutors). This article adds information on a collaborative learning program that aimed to reach integration between theory and practice (the design, knowledge, and skills/performance). Student enjoyed the clinical reasoning course, but tutors need more training to be ready for a collaborative learning program.
Matsuyama, Y., Nakaya, M., Okazaki, H., Lebowitz, A. J., &Leppink, J. (2019)	Does changing from a teacher-centered to a learner-centered context promote self- regulated learning: a qualitative study in a Japanese undergraduate setting.	(Equity between students-teachers). This article adds on how SCL encourages the development of self-directed learning. The SCL impacts on equity in learning partnershiprelationship and adds a consideration on students' motivation through the paradigm.
Mcdowell, J., Styles, K., Sewell, K., Trinder, P., Marriott, J., Maher, S., & Naidu, S. (2016)	Instructional design and assessment a simulated learning environment for teaching medicine dispensing skills.	(The importance of engaging students). A study to evaluate a web-based tool that simulated the real situation in dispensing drugs. This tool was used together with a tutorial session. The innovative strategy as part of SCL was created to support the learning process which is also highlighted on learning environment safety.

	<p>Pittenger, A. L., Dimitropoulos, E., Foag, J., Bishop, D., Panizza, S., & Bishop, J. R. (2019)</p> <p>Pittenger, A. L., Fierke, K. K., Kostka, S., & Jardine, P. J. (2016)</p> <p>Sonne, S., Kjaer, C., Möller, S., & Bloksgaard, M. (2020)</p>	<p>Closing the classroom theory to practice gap by simulating a psychiatric pharmacy practice experience.</p> <p>Developing interprofessional facilitators and leaders: utilization of advanced health profession students as interprofessional (IPE) facilitators.</p> <p>Implementing collaborative, active learning using peer instructions in pharmacology teaching increases students' learning and thereby exam performance.</p>	<p>(One of strategy for engaging students is using 4CID model). This article adds information on innovation by using 4CID in delivering "hard" material in pharmacology i.e., psychiatric topics. Adding information on the consequences of using SCL that there was significant increasing of faculty workload but proven to stimulate self-directed learning.</p> <p>(Equity of learning). This article adds on peer learning, evaluating the IPE program that uses peer learning by seeing its effectiveness. Peer learning could be used as one strategy for facilitating IPE - advanced, the senior students continue with the community with their own aims that are shaped through the program. This study elaborates the equity of learning.</p> <p>(Student-engagement in learning). This article highlighted collaborative teaching and learning while also adapting a flipped classroom in preparing a quiz followed by lecture (added also Poll during the lecture). This article adds on its effectiveness in facilitating a learning process in pharmacology. This article aimed to enhance students' engagement throughout the course.</p>
<p>Cultural and community need awareness.</p>	<p>Abllah, Z., Haizan, S., Kamar, S., Abdul, N., Supaat, S., Firdaus, M., & Musa, C. (2019)</p> <p>Almetwazi, M., Alhammad, A., Alhossan, A., & Alturki, H. (2020)</p>	<p>The impact of community learning programs on Kuantan dental students.</p> <p>Pharmacy students' satisfaction with introductory pharmacy practice experiences (IPPE) at community pharmacy : the case of Saudi Arabia.</p>	<p>(Community service to endorse students' reflection of community needs). This study proves that tapping into the unique culture/system of a community helps effective learning in collaboration and civilian responsibilities. Community service is proven to be effective to offer students the opportunity to learn in a real life setting with additional advantages such as deeper understanding on social problems, insight in values, gaining new attitude and skills. But it also acknowledges the abundant effort needed to establish the strategy - more budget, more facilities, more time and resources.</p> <p>(Community service to endorse students' reflection of community needs). Community service, as a part of mentorship strategy could be used to facilitate the enhancement of students' ability in dispensing and counseling skills. Nevertheless, it also acknowledged that this strategy brings resource consequences.</p>

	Garbarino, J. T., &Foran, L. (2020)	Nurse education in practice the impact of a gerontology nursing course with a service-learning component on student attitudes towards working with older adults: a mixed methods study	(Community service to endorse students' reflection of community needs). This study proves that service learning as part of the SCL strategy could increase students' ability on how to interact with elderly population.
	Stagg, D. L., &McCarthy, J. (2020)	Service learning: a method of instruction for community health content in nursing curriculums.	(Community service to endorse students' reflection of community needs). This study adds a prove of effectiveness of service learning (as much as like COME/CBE) that could facilitate learning to be able to empathize, respect more to community health activity, collaborate, exposure of real situation and, highlight the threat of privacy
	Zanchetta, M., Schwind, J., Aksenchuk, K., Gorospe, F. F., & Santiago, L. (2013)	Nurse education today an international internship on social development led by Canadian nursing students: empowering learning	(Community service to endorse students' reflection of community needs). This study provides gain in service learning - an internship could help facilitate the student to gain cultural competency and sense on health inequalities in certain communities. Faculty-students partnership through the whole process, provide faculty monitoring-supervision-feedback individually to sustain students' motivation and engagements throughout the process.
	Marques, T., Baldoni, D. O., & Campos, M. (2019)	A distance-learning course to improve drug-dispensing behaviors among Brazilian community pharmacists.	(Training community practitioners). This study adds information on innovative strategies in facilitating learning, the aim of the program is to increase community-pharmacists' ability in dispensing the drugs - more to skills but the results showed that the program only works on knowledge level with additional ability to collaborate.
	Schneider, A. R., Stephens, L. A. M., Catalina, S., Marín, O., &Semenic, S. (2018)	Nurse education in practice benefits and challenges of a nursing service-learning partnership with a community of internally displaced persons in Colombia.	(Community needs awareness). This study is a prove that service learning (such look like COME/CBE) give advantages for student to learn social determinant of health, development of compassion, - in touch with community appreciation of nursing roles, community engagement - professional development with thread of moral distress, lack of professional value, conflict, its sustainability.
Reflective learning and Professionalism	Bajis, D., Chaar, B., Basheti, I. A., & Moles, R. (2019)	Pharmacy students' medication history taking competency: simulation and feedback learning intervention.	(Reflective learning in a hierarchical setting). This article adds information on innovative strategy simulation with feedback and role plays in increasing students' communication skills and taking medication histories.

Fejzic, J., & Barker, M. (2015)	Implementing simulated learning modules to improve students' pharmacy practice skills and professionalism.	(Learning Professionalism). This article adds on proof effectiveness on SCL, especially in delivering the communication skills in which using the ABCD approach. All results (quantitative and qualitative) support its effectiveness.
Hsieh, J., Kuo LC., & Wang YW. (2019)	Learning medical professionalism – the application of appreciative inquiry and social media.	(Facilitating learning professionalism). The course was appreciated by the students and highlight on appreciative inquiry which need to be more integrated within the culture. This article adds information on strategies in facilitating professionalism using social media.
Li, S., Ye, X., & Chen, W. (2019)	Nurse education in practice and effectiveness of “nursing case-based learning” course on nursing students' critical thinking ability: a comparative study.	(Facilitating characters of professionalism). This article adds how innovative strategy could facilitate the development of critical thinking ability. The innovation was case based strategy - much more like a problem-based learning. With a quantitative approach, the study uses critical thinking disposition inventory/ CTDI inventory in several measurements. The CTDI consists of truth-seeking, open-mindedness, analyticity, systematicity, self-confidence, inquisitiveness, and maturity.
Remington, T. L., Bleske, B. E., Bartholomew, T., Dorsch, M. P., Guthrie, S. K., Klein, K. C., Tingen, J. M., & Wells, T. D. (2017)	Qualitative analysis of student perceptions comparing team-based learning and traditional lecture in a pharmacotherapeutics course.	(Reflective learning). This article adds information on effectiveness of team-based learning (a comparative cross over research) - team based learning as part of an innovative strategy that could facilitate a certain level of students' learning process, and further give additional advantages such as critical skills, collaborative skills.
Rebitch, C. B., Fleming, V. H., Palmer, R., & Rong, H. (2019)	Evaluation of video-enhanced case-based activities guided by the pharmacists' patient care process.	(Facilitating professional clinical performance). This article adds a prove on how innovative strategy using video case-based activities(Pharmacy-patient care process) could facilitate the development of pharmacist students (especially in clinical ability - to decide to use the knowledge).
Gordon, M., Fell, C. W. R., Box, H., Farrell, M., & Stewart, A. (2017)	Learning health ‘safety’ within non-technical skills interprofessional simulation education: a qualitative study.	(Facilitating characters of professionalism). This article adds on innovative strategy (simulation of IPE – nontechnical skills enhance level of medical safety/ TEANSELS) that built upon SECTORS models - showed that this simulation could "touch" theme on

Vos, S. S., Sabus, A., Seyfer, J., Umlah, L., Gross-advani, C., & Thompson-oster, J. (2018) Using continuing professional development to create meaningful co-curricular learning opportunities for all student pharmacists.

analytical skills, professional behavior, communication, teamwork, context, and pedagogy with subcodes on social skills, error awareness, affective attributes, decision making.

(Facilitating learning professionalism). This article provides evidence on how SCL could facilitate the development of professionalism for pharmacists. Using experiential learning framework which applied in the community, by only using reflection throughout time, this strategy could facilitate professionalism development (professional services, leadership, and community engagement).

'Equity in learning or active participation'

The interaction between teachers, learners and the learning environment determines the overall success of any teaching and learning process. The SCL paradigm places great importance in maintaining an equal relationship between teachers and learners throughout the learning process (Harden and Liley, 2018; Albanese, 2000; Dolmans, et al., 2015). This partnership in learning is determined by student-teacher interdependence and respect for one another, as well as students' active participation throughout the process of learning as mentioned by Dewantara (Tauchid, et al., 1962). The balance between student autonomy and teacher direction will shape students' experience and guide students' motivation to achieve specific desired outcomes.

In the compilation of Dewantara's article by his direct apprentices Tauchid and colleagues (1962), teacher and student attitude and motivation prior to any classes were frequently emphasized, usually with Javanese expressions such as '*Neng (Meneng/ be quiet) – Ning (Wening/ be smart) – Nung (Hanung/ be generous) – Nang (Wenang/ have integrity)*' (calm in mind and listening carefully, smart in thinking, understanding, and cautiousness in action). One of Dewantara's famous messages was 'Everyone is a teacher, and every house is a school,' in which he accentuated that education can be done everywhere by everyone and started at home. Therefore, in his viewpoint, parents, and future parents (meaning, the young generations) should be aware of the importance of their behavior, as it will become a role model for their future children. As such, the education system begins at home and in the family, long before children attend school classroom. In his articles, Dewantara also wrote many times about family and the function of each family member and the psychological background of a family interaction.

In the current SCL approach, there are two main forms of student-teacher partnership relationship. The first is in a longitudinal mentorship program, whereby the same teacher mentors the same students throughout the curriculum. The second is in a short-term facilitation of learning, in which different teachers interact with different students, at every class or group discussion. In this review, we found 13 articles striving for 'equity' between teachers and learners from Europe, Southeast Asia, and North America regions.

Examples of student-teacher longitudinal mentorship programs demonstrated in studies from European region in nursing education explained that the student-teacher relationship in a mentorship program was challenging, but should be continuously encouraged. Williamson from England found that collaborative mentorship and coaching of nursing students was beneficial, in which the feedback and learning direction could be gained through peers rather than focusing only from the teacher (Williamson et al., 2020). Similarly, Hill (2020) found the effectiveness of collaborative learning with specific attention to teacher-student ratio. The proper ratio is important regarding a challenge of "learning to fly," which means a good mentorship program should prepare the students to be independent learners, to become independent yet responsible individuals in the future. Emery (2019) explained that mentorship for undergraduate researchers in an ecological context, the applicable delivery of feedback and gradual steps for mentee enrollment should be established. Additionally, a study with dental students reported that peer assisted learning in a flipped classroom of online and offline methods was well received by students and tutors (Quoß, et al., 2017).

To approach the student-teacher equal relationships during short-term classes, adequate preparation of teachers, to prepare the learning material, learning strategy, and ample time to interact with the students are highly important. However, lack of preparation of teachers are still challenges found in this review. Examples are as follows: a study from the US with pharmacy students, explained the unprepared teachers with an abundance of work could loosen the comprehensiveness of delivering the learning material during classes. Consequently, there is less space to interact with students (Pittenger et al., 2019). While in medicine, a study in facilitating pharmacological concepts with European students also recognized unprepared teachers in delivering the content are teachers who used the same slide and optimizing the use of information technology (Sonne et al., 2020). A study in Singapore found a threat to teachers' readiness for SCL. Although this study reported that students enjoyed the collaborative learning program, teachers felt they needed more time to nurture individual students (Ignatio et al., 2020). To interact with students in a more partnership relationship, or to involve the students to participate in their learning goals and strategies, teachers need sufficient preparation time to prepare their lessons. Interaction, participation feedback, and reflective learning should also be explicit agendas in the learning design that teachers will deliver. Therefore, appropriate time to construct the learning design will help teachers to be ready for student-centered learning approach.

However, elaboration on learning towards behavior should be followed with systematic specific steps on learning preparations. The current SCL principle encourage both teacher and student to have ample time for preparation prior to the learning sessions (Dolmans, et al., 2015). Reading tasks, quizzes, formulation of learning goals are examples of stimulation before or after learning sessions. A study from Japan highlighted that

students' motivation becomes the ultimate factor that teachers should continuously stimulate, and this stimulation needs comprehensive instructional design for learning to be internalized into students' aptitude (Matsuyama et al., 2019). Teachers need to be aware of students' preparedness to learn, which should also be encouraged in both the mentorship program and the short-term encounters in every class.

‘Cultural and community’s need awareness’

Contextual learning is one of key component of the student-centered learning (Harden and Liley, 2018). Dewantara used to teach his students by optimizing local learning resources such as farms and crop field (rice, corn), waters resources (pond, river, small lake) nearby the schools, including local arts and culture (folk songs, traditional dances, fables, and drama)(Tauchid, et al., 1962).He asked the students to observe different kind of animal, their daily habits and habitat, and to observe specific evolution, for example: the life cycle of a butterfly or a frog which has metamorphose phases. Dewantara also stimulated students to develop senses of arts, by listening, observing, and drawing by usage of local arts like folk songs, *gamelan* music, and *batik* paintings skills which are specific to the culture where the students live. Also, to stimulate students’ physical exercise by training local marital art like *pencak silat*. When teaching an Indonesian map, Dewantara asked the students to make a miniature of Sumatera, Java, Kalimantan, Bali, Sulawesi, and Papua islands from molding used newspapers, and then asked them to identify; with certain nuts, where big cities and capitals in each province lie on those islands. By actively participating in the learning process through many activities that resemble surroundings environment and culture, memory retention of students will last longer, rather than if they only read a book or writing what the teacher dictated for them. Students were observing, reflecting on what they did, and finding meaning of new knowledge, skills, and attitude by themselves. In a separate book, Dewantara elaborate the importance of art and culture as interplay factors to education (Tauchid et al., 1962b). Therefore, in Indonesia, the ministry which oversee national education is usually called as the Ministry of Education and Culture, up to today. According to Dewantara, education and culture influence one another in a type of feedback loop. Good education helps form good habits, which ultimately cultivate a solid culture. At the same time, good livelihood and culture will influence a better process of education.

This kind of context and culturally sensitive learning strategies, as demonstrated by Dewantara, are similarly needed for current medical teachers' creativity to manage the learning process. Innovative strategies in facilitating learning should be created and managed for every aspect of knowledge that medical teachers should deliver. In health professions education with SCL paradigm, strategies in facilitating learning should consider the context (the science and the environment) and enhancement for reflective practice. In this study, we found seven articles related to cultural and community need awareness. For medical curriculum, community-based learning is an endorsement of social accountability of a medical school to also participate, contribute, and involving the community for preparing future doctors that could fulfil community needs (Boelen, et al., 2016).

Countries have their own cultures, which might bring specific environments and lead to challenges in implementing SCL. Several captured innovation strategies have been applied, such as the I-COREE model (participatory action research) (Nguyen-Truong et al., 2018), CLIPS (Collaborative Learning in Practice) (Williamson et al., 2020), SECTORS models (patient-safety through simulation and interprofessional) (Gordon et al., 2017), ICM-cyPAL (peer learning) (Quoß et al., 2017), PPCP (Pharmacist patient-care process) (Rebitch et al., 2019). TBL (team-based learning), Participation Action Research (PAR), and Service Learning (COME/CBE) were also used to facilitate certain desired outcomes (Remington et al., 2017).

References about ‘contextual learning’, as articulated by Dewantara, were also found in current different cultural contexts, professions, and countries. We found that, regardless of cultural characteristics, most countries have already tried to apply an innovative strategy towards SCL. The main outcome was professionalism (Marques et al., 2019) and responsibility towards cultural and community needs (Abdallah et al., 2019; Almetwazi et al., 2020; Schneider, 2018). Most of the studies reported their success in delivering the outcome with additional expected results, such as advanced understanding of social determinants of health (Zanchetta, 2013; Schneider, 2018), collaborative and critical skills (Remington, 2017; Stagg, 2020); communication skills (Garbarino, 2020); and compassion (Garbarino, 2020; Stagg, 2020). Nevertheless, the studies also emphasized the extensive resources required, such as in facilities, budget, teacher, and student effort (Abdallah et al., 2019), and transportation (Stagg, 2018). Studies found conflict distresses with professional development (Schneider, 2018; Stagg, 2018. Abdallah et al., 2019), and overall lack in faculty readiness (Almetwazi et al., 2020; Zanchetta, 2013).

In addition to contextual learning is the use of information technology, which has become the new worldwide culture. A significant use of information technology is the distance learning program, which has become increasingly popular during Covid-19 pandemic. One study reported that the use of distance learning adds more

engagement to the teaching-learning process (Marques et al., 2019). Ideal distance learning programs provide reading resources as well as learning instructions or tasks to the students, and not only one-way lecture without ample time for preparation for students and teachers. Adequate opportunities for interaction before, during, and after distance learning classes also determine the results of the learning process. Feedback and reflection for and from teachers, students, and peers, are still keys for better learning that are also important to be explicitly scheduled during a distance learning program. Synchronous, asynchronous sessions should be prepared sufficiently. Our review, however, we did not include the studies during pandemic (after 2020) because it was out of our scope.

‘Reflective learning and professionalism’

According to Dewantara, any mistakes made by students should be reflected with necessary awareness of better learning process in the future, and not emphasizing on unconstructive punishment (Tauchid, et al., 1962). Reflective learning already introduced by Dewantara when teaching his students in the early 19th century, in a context which is highly paternalistic, where teacher-student dialogue was rare, and presumably was also self-reflection. Dewantara encouraged his students to have high moral attitude with full awareness of what they do, which should be bound to any professions they will cherish in the future. At that time, he already called this attitudinal learning process as ‘a character building’ (Tauchid, et al., 1962). Today, in medical education, we know the term of ‘professionalism.’ Professionalism would be part of inserting the value within the profession and its related virtues, such as physician's altruism, trustworthiness, compassion, and moral integrity. Also, each profession within each of the allied health professions has common characteristics such as excellence, patient-centered care, honesty and integrity, diversity and inclusion, respect and teamwork, humanism, autonomy, and social justice.

As professionalism will be the foremost outcome of health professions education as seen by others, including the patients as the clients, medical teachers need to facilitate and nurture medical students' personal and professional character. The recommended international medical education competences stated complex skills as the main abilities of medical doctors, rather than only emphasizing on medical knowledge (CanMEDS; WFME). To facilitate the acquisition of complex abilities, such as teamwork, communication, health literacy, and health education, students should be gradually exposed to real life situation but with satisfactory supervision and constructive feedback. In this study, we found eight studies discussing facilitating character development of future medical doctors, which we categorized into two themes: using community-based educational settings or using other innovative learning strategies.

Three studies reported using the community as a basis for a student's best learning professionalism experience. Studies in medicine fields focused more on compassion and building relationships as core competency development of professionalism through specific communities (Schneider et al., 2018; Garbarino et al., 2020). While for nursing and pharmacists, a community-based learning strategy was used to facilitate professionalism development (Vos et al., 2018). Other strategy to stimulate professionalism learning approaches were reported by medicine and pharmacist fields. In pharmacists, studies reported a technology-based strategy to learn about dispensing skills, and a role-play-based strategy on feedback, which focuses on encouraging communication abilities (McDowell, 2016; Bajis, 2019). While in medicine, a study reported role-play strategy in facilitating communication and the use of social media to facilitate appreciative inquiry (Fejzic et al., 2015). However, based on complexity of professionalism, these studies explored part of professional development characters, such as communication skills (including appreciative inquiry, building relationships, showing compassion, and cultural awareness), the role of a profession (decision making, dispensing drugs) (Rebitch et al., 2019; McDowell, 2016), and development of other soft skills prior to professionalism (Li, et al., 2019).

Discussions

We have sought to demonstrate three main propositions between student-centered learning principles and Dewantara's educational pillars. First, SCL's idea of interdependence and mutual respect between teachers and learners are reflective of Dewantara's pillar of equity between learners and teachers. Second, innovative strategies employed by teachers to fully engage students mirror Dewantara's incorporation culturally and contextually sensitive learning. Ultimately, both current SCL principles and oldies Dewantara's values place a high importance on reflective learning as a way to embody professionalism.

Partnership in learning can exist when two factors are present: Teachers' facilitation and being open toward students' learning plan, and students can self-direct their learning by reflecting on any feedback from teachers and peers. To attain this partnership interaction, we should pay attention to teacher preparedness in designing

learning experiences to achieve learning outcomes and student motivation. The direct relationship between the two factors is that the more teachers are prepared, the more students are motivated to engage. Formulation of learning goals by students, can only be done with suitable support from the teachers by means of stimulating motivation, reflection, and coaching.

Zimmerman et al. (2014) proposed enhanced communication practices for effective student-centered learning. The facilitation of learning could be done by adequate and continuous teacher-student dialogue. Lack of dialogue is the first step to overcome, especially in a hierarchical cultural setting where teacher-student power-distance gap is wide (Soemantri, et al., 2022; Sari et al., 2023). Possible pitfalls are students frequently attend with desired learning experience while the teachers prepare for other learning outcomes. In this study, we found that the less the teachers exhibit preparedness and perseverance in facilitating learning, the lower the student motivation (Zanchetta, et al., 2013; Quöß, et al., 2017; Matsuyama, 2019; Pittenger, et al., 2019; Abdallah et al., 2019; Ignacio and Chen, 2020; Almetwazi et al., 2020). To our surprise, these studies were done in countries with a more partnership culture, which were not excluded to the challenges of establishing the partnership relationship in learning. There are authority and responsibility distributions within a learning curve.

The attainable solution is to nurture active participation of the students during learning. Zanchetta et al. (2013) suggest reforms in teacher-student interaction to nurture active role-playing in establishing positive relationships. Dewantara had already employed many role-playing methods in teaching students from elementary up to high school to understand basic knowledge such as physics, geography, biology, and socio-economy. Dewantara might not explicitly discuss the importance of dialogical process between teacher-student as what Dewey did, but he role-modelled it as explained in the results. A result of dialogical relationship which is the democracy in learning, as one of Dewey's origins, also strongly emphasized in lots of his articles (Tauchid, et al., 1962). The effort to build an equal relationship between teachers and students is mainly based on respect, mutual relationship, and active participation from different parties, which are the ultimate challenges for the wide-power distance culture. As mentioned in previous publications, 'Dewantara' is a lay people name, he (with full awareness) purposefully removed his royal family name to impede the social hierarchy between him and his students. When he received 'a doctorate of honoris causa' from the top-rank university in Indonesia in 1956, he clearly stated to his apprentices to never write it down to avoid differences with others (Tauchid, et al., 1962; Claramita, et al., 2020). This kind of attitude was meant to be an example on a teacher-student partnership initiative. However, recent followers may try to use his new name as a new rank in educational title, in which this phenomenon shows that Dewantara's message remains misplaced in the cultural context of wide power-distance.

As leaders in the teaching and learning process with a higher level of complex knowledge, teachers should be able to deliver, direct, assess, facilitate, and manage the learning resources toward the students' learning goal attainment. In turn, efforts made by teachers to facilitate learning should be met with students' high level of motivation to both self-direct their learning process and receive feedback from teachers and peers. A balanced teacher-student contribution in learning is necessary, like a tango-dancing process. Therefore, teachers were challenged in their creativity and perseverance while facilitating the learning process, especially to engage the students with the learning themes. Set in the 1900s, Dewantara primarily used local cultural events and arts to help students comprehend essential listening and observation skills. In this study we found recent innovative strategies for teaching and learning activities, such as peer-learning (ICM-cyPAL), team-based learning (PPCP), collaborative learning (CLIPS and SECTORS), participatory action research (I-COREE), and many community-based learning combining education and services to specific community members, as portrayed in Table 3. In present day, the use of information technology to engage the students to contribute actively to their learning process can be done through social media (Facebook to train appreciative inquiry), or specific technology to facilitate learning (MyDispence) – all of which were not available during Dewantara's time.

Another factor in facilitating SCL is a well-prepared instructional design. In the SCL paradigm, instructional design should be arranged based on its context, the science (content), and the setting (environment-culture). To optimize the learning effect for students, a chance for reflective learning should be put in place. Teacher-learner relationship will affect how the feedback could be accepted and perceived, leading to virtuous reflection (Soemantri et al., 2022, Findyartini, et al., 2023). As part of the previously discussed student-centered learning concept, an equal mutual relationship based on vigorous observation will support a more partnership relationship. All those learning strategies in a community-based attachment draw back the need and support for implementing professionalism and reflective practice. The complex task and instruction should be given and monitored throughout the process, in which boarding schools can be one of the ways to overcome the need for much effort to implement such a complex learning process, as stated in Abllah (2019). Besides that,

transportation becomes the primary support for community-based learning or service learning to keep students safe during the learning process (Stagg et al., 2018), therefore, a boarding schools can be the solution.

One of student-character-building approaches of Dewantara is reflected in his “brotherhood” concept. He created multiple series of peer-learning within the Schools of Taman-Siswa, in which the peer-learning or collaboration between students became a peer society, exceeded the learning sessions, and lasted longer, even when the pupil became alumni of the schools. The strength of a collectivistic culture is the 'brotherhood' feeling that was well-nurtured in Taman Siswa's educational environment, which was mostly done within a boarding school system. The current example of a well-established Taman Siswa school was the Taman Taruna Nusantara High School at Middle Java, Indonesia. Established in 1993, the school has more than 10,000 alumni who help each other in an intact and well-organized community group (Parmi, 2009). In building the school, Dewantara likely adopted the shape and form of Santi Niketan school by Mahatma Gandhi in India (Tauchid, et al., 1962). This kind of brotherhood-ness and apprenticeship-ness in a long-term dormitory system (*nyantrik*) are likely the chosen educational system in the old Asian countries, including Indonesia. As Dewantara mentioned, “A school is a home of a Guru (teacher) where students will come to and learn.” In this arrangement, parents entrusted their children to the hands of the teachers and have them live together for a period of time, so that these students may be trained in knowledge, religion, life skills or other specific skills (marital art, farming, animal husbandry, fishery), as well as being exposed to high moral values (Tauchid, et al., 1962). The world's history renowned this community-based boarding school system, for example in China (i.e., Shaolin system) and India (i.e., Gandhi system), and in Indonesia (i.e., Mandala Kadewaguruan), long before 1000 AD. Dewantara himself was also part of a peer community-practice group of wiseman noble persons called ‘Selasa-Kliwon group’ in which they met every Tuesday-Kliwon/ per six week based on Javanese calendar to discuss national needs issues, especially education (Tauchid, et al., 1962).

Continuous brotherhood-ness was not found in our scoping review. It seems that modern schools emphasize more on personal and professional development, rather than collective community practice. We think that any community group of practice, which can help their members continuously, are well represented practice of impact in education. Therefore a ‘brotherhood’ phenomenon, a continuous relationship among alumni, students, teachers, and community, could be enhanced for the future modern SCL paradigm.

In medical education, 'boarding school' can be described as the clinical program or post-graduate residential program, whereby the ‘Does’ level of the Miller Pyramid or when students meet real patients and doing clinical services under supervision was done (Miller, 1990). This clinical education stages, which can last three to five years depend on each specialization, already occurs during the two clinical years of undergraduate medical education. The terminology “residents” refer to registrar doctors or future specialists who stays in the hospital, or in other health care facilities, for an extended period of time to help the patients. This phenomenon explains a strong sense of collegiality in medical education up to the professional work of medical doctors.

However, our review found that clinical education was not adequately supported by the involved staff due to a lack of received information comprehension of the learning process and its instruction, as reported as a lack of faculty readiness to provide constructive feedback (Almetwazi et al., 2020; Zanchetta, et al., 2013). Therefore, besides preparing the facilitation, faculty development programs should be arranged in detail and evaluated in terms of their effectiveness in supporting various staff needs while facilitating the learning process. Observation-based learning is central in a program that will produce a profession with solid collegiality. A highly engaged faculty members in health education and health care services is essential to better student-centered learning, which in turn contributes toward better patient-centered care services. When students realize that they are prioritized in their learning goals and activities, and involved in the overall learning process, they will grow accustomed to having mutual dialogue with teachers and peers, fostering an open mind, and cultivating a collaborative attitude. Prioritizing the students will in turn will prime them to build future work environments that prioritize patients at the center and encourage participation and dialogue for a more effective clinical decision making that leads to better health outcome.

Conclusions

Based on the literature included in this scoping review, we appreciated that Dewantara could articulate the need for ‘equity’ in the student-teacher relationship, ‘cultural awareness’ and ‘reflective practice’, long before the term ‘student-centered learning’ became popular, even in the medical and health professions education. These core values of Dewantara are aligned with the present student-centered learning (SCL) principles, as demonstrated in this scoping review. A higher regard for Dewantara's core principles, which intersects a lot with SCL, can positively impact the overall teaching and learning process. Special attention should be paid to teachers' preparedness and students' participation in learning, which requires constructive feedback, reflection,

and motivation. Additionally, SCL could nurture peer-group and collegiality from undergraduate education up to community-practice. More studies should be nourished to bring locally rooted evidence for future global education.

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Ethical clearance

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Albanese M. (2000). Problem-based learning: why curricula are likely to show little effect on knowledge and clinical skills. *Medical Education*, 34(9):729-38. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2923.2000.00753.x. Erratum in: *Medical Education*(2001), 35(4):419.
- Abllah, Z., Sayed-kamar, S.H., Halim, N. A., Supaat, S., & Che-Musa, M.F. (2019). The impact of community learning program to a Kuantan dental students. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 16, 2262–2267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2019.06.119>
- Almetwazi, M., Alhammad, A., Alhossan, A., & Alturki, H. (2020). Pharmacy students’ satisfaction with Introductory Pharmacy Practice Experiences (IPPE) at community pharmacy: The case of Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, 28(1), 68–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsps.2019.11.006>
- Bajis, D., Chaar, B., Basheti, I. A., & Moles, R. (2019). Pharmacy students’ medication history taking competency: Simulation and feedback learning intervention. *Currents in Pharmacy Teaching and Learning*, 11(10), 1002–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cptl.2019.06.007>
- Bhayat, A., &Mahrous, M. S. (2012). Impact of outreach activities at the College of Dentistry, Taibah University. *Journal of Taibah University Medical Sciences*, 7(1), 19–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtumed.2012.07.008>
- Boelen C, Pearson D, Kaufman A, Rourke J, Woollard R, Marsh DC., & Gibbs T. (2016). Producing a socially accountable medical school: AMEE Guide No. 109. *Medical Teacher*,38(11):1078-1091. doi: 10.1080/0142159X.2016.1219029.
- Bronowski, J. (2010). *Student-Centered Learning*. *European Student Union*. 1–72. <https://www.esu-online.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/100814-SCL.pdf>
- Can-MEDS. <https://www.royalcollege.ca/ca/en/canmeds/about-canmeds.html>
- Claramita, M., Nugraheni, M.D., van Dalen, J., &van der Vleuten, C. (2013). Doctor-patient communication in Southeast Asia: a different culture? *Advances Health Sciences Education Theory &Practice*, 18(1):15-31. doi: 10.1007/s10459-012-9352-5.
- Claramita M., Prabandari Y., Graber A., &Scherpbier A. (2020). Challenges of Communication Skills Transfer of Medical Students in the Cultural Context of Indonesia. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-based Learning*, 14 (1) <https://doi.org/10.14434/ijpbl.v14i1.28594>
- Claramita, M. Revealing “Tut WuriHandayani” - a student-centred learning approach - by Ki Hajar Dewantarafrom the early 20th Century: A Literature Review. (2016). *Indonesian Medical Educationjournal*,5(1) 2016:1-14.
- Dolmans, D., Michaelsen, L., van Merriënboer, J., &van der Vleuten, C. (2015). Should we choose between problem-based learning and team-based learning? No, combine the best of both worlds! *Medical Teacher*, 37(4):354-9. doi: 10.3109/0142159X.2014.948828.
- Emery, N., Hund, A., Duffy, M., &Swei, A. (2019). *Students as ecologists: Strategies for successful mentorship of undergraduate researchers*. Pp. 4316–4326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.5090>
- Fejzic, J., & Barker, M. (2015). Implementing simulated learning modules to improve students’ pharmacy practice skills and professionalism.*Pharmacy Practice*13(3), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.18549/2015.03.583>.

- Findyartini, A., Syah N.A., Susilo, AP., Nurokhmanti H, Qomariyah N, Greviana N., Sari S.M., Ainin., D.Q &Claramita M.(2023).Challenges and opportunities in cultivating medical students' competencies: Participatory action research from a hierarchical cultural setting. *Medical Education Online*, 28(1) <https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2023.2185122>
- Garbarino, J. T., &Foran, L. (2020). Nurse Education in Practice The impact of a gerontology nursing course with a service-learning component on student attitudes towards working with older adults : A mixed methods study. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 42, 102684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.102684>
- Gordon, M., Fell, C. W. R., Box, H., Farrell, M., & Stewart, A. (2017). Learning health 'safety ' within non-technical skills interprofessional simulation education : a qualitative study. *Medical Education Online*, 22(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2017.1272838>
- Hanson, M. H., Amato, A., Durani, A., Hoyden, J. R., Koe, S., Sheagren, E., & Yang, Y. (2021).Participating through Revolution: Dewantara. In *Creativity and improvised educations: Case studies for understanding impact and implications* (pp. 164–196). essay, Routledge.
- Harden RM. Ten key features of the future medical school-not an impossible dream. (2018). *Medical Teacher*, 40(10):1010-1015. doi: 10.1080/0142159X.2018.1498613.
- Harden, R.M.,& Crosby, J. (2000). AMEE Guide No 20: The good teacher is more than a lecturer - the twelve roles of the teacher. *Medical Teacher*, 22(4): 334-347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/014215900409429>
- Harden, R.M.,&Liley, P. (2018). *Eight roles of medical teachers: The purpose and function of a medical teacher in the healthcare professions*.Elsevier pub. eBook ISBN: 9780702068942
- Hickman, L., Neubert, S., & Reich, K. (2009). *John Dewey between pragmatism and constructivism*. Fordham University Press.
- Hill, R., Woodward, M., & Arthur, A. (2020). Nurse Education Today Collaborative Learning in Practice (CLIP): Evaluation of a new approach to clinical learning. *Nurse Education Today*, 85(July 2019), 104295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2019.104295>
- Hsieh, J.G., Kuo LC., &Wang, Y.W. (2019). Learning medical professionalism - the application of appreciative inquiry and social media. *Medical Education Online*, 24(1):1586507. doi: 10.1080/10872981.2019.1586507.
- Hing, L.K. (1978). The Taman Siswa in Postwar Indonesia. *Indonesia*, 1(25):41-59. New York: Cornell Univ Southeast Asia Program Pub.
- Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing cultures: the Hofstede model in context. *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture*, 2(1):2307–919. <https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1014>.
- Ignacio, J., & Chen, H. (2020). Nurse Education Today Cognitive integration in health professions education : Development and implementation of a collaborative learning workshop in an undergraduate nursing program. *Nurse Education Today*, 90(June 2019), 104436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2020.104436>
- Keiler, L.S. (2018). Teachers' roles and identities in student-centered classrooms. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 5, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-018-0131-6>
- Kreider, C. M., Medina, S., Lan, M., Wu, C., Percival, S. S., Byrd, C. E., Delislie, A., Schoenfelder, D., & Mann, W. C. (2018). *Beyond Academics: A Model for Simultaneously Advancing Campus-Based Supports for Learning Disabilities, STEM Students' Skills for Self-Regulation, and Mentors' Knowledge for Co-regulating and Guiding*. 9(August), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01466>
- Kreider, C.M., Medina, S., Lan, M.F., Wu, C.Y., Percival, S.S., Byrd, C.E.,Delislie, A., Schoenfelder, D., &Mann, W.C. Beyond Academics: A Model for Simultaneously Advancing Campus-Based Supports for Learning Disabilities, STEM Students' Skills for Self-Regulation, and Mentors' Knowledge for Co-regulating and Guiding. *Front Psychol*, 17(9):1466. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01466.
- Koe SC. (2020). *The ecosystem of imagination: Tracing the influences behind the Father of Indonesian Education*. Masters of Humanitarian, Columbia University.
- Li, S., Ye, X., & Chen, W. (2019). Nurse Education in Practice Practice and e ff ectiveness of “ nursing case-based learning ” course on nursing student ’ s critical thinking ability : A comparative study. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 36(759), 91–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.03.007>
- Marques, Dos Reis, T., de Oliveira Baldoni, A., Campos, A.M., Giroto, E., Guidoni, C.M., Obrelino, P.R.,&Leira Pereira L,R, A. (2019). Distance-Learning Course to Improve Drug-Dispensing Behaviors Among Brazilian Community Pharmacists. *American Journal Pharmacy Education*, 83(8):6874. doi: 10.5688/ajpe6874
- Matsuyama, Y., Nakaya, M., Okazaki, H. et al.(2019). Does changing from a teacher-centered to a learner-centered context promote self-regulated learning: a qualitative study in a Japanese undergraduate setting. *BMC Medical Education*, 19, 152.<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-019-1550-x>
- McDowell, J., Styles, K., Sewell, K., Trinder, P., Marriott, J., Maher, S., &Naidu, S. (2016). A simulated Learning Environment for Teaching Medicine Dispensing Skills. *American Journal Pharmacy Education*, 25;80(1):11. doi: 10.5688/ajpe80111.

- McVey, R.T. (1967). *Taman Siswa and the Indonesian national awakening*. *Indonesia*, 1(4):128-49. New York: Cornell Univ Southeast Asia Program Pub.
- Miller, G.E. (1990). The assessment of clinical skills/competence/performance. *Academic Medicine*, 65(9 Suppl):S63-7. doi: 10.1097/00001888-199009000-00045.
- Nguyen-truong, C. K. Y., Fritz, R. L., Lee, J., Lau, C., Le, C., Kim, J., Leung, H., Nguyen, T. H., Leung, J., Le, T. V., Truong, A. M., Postma, J., Hoeksel, R., & Son, C. Van. (2018). *Interactive CO-learning for Research Engagement and Education (I-COREE) Curriculum to Build Capacity Between Community Partners and Academic Researchers*. *Asian Pacific Island Nursing Journal*, 3(4): 126–138. doi: [10.31372/20180304.1030](https://doi.org/10.31372/20180304.1030)
- Nicklen, P., Rivers, G., Ooi, C., Ilic, D., Reeves, S., & Walsh, K., et al. (2016) An Approach for Calculating Student-Centered Value in Education – A Link between Quality, Efficiency, and the Learning Experience in the Health Professions. *PLoS ONE*, 11(9): e0162941. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0162941>
- O’Neill, G., & McMahon, T. (2005). *Student-centered learning: What does it mean for students and teachers?* In: *Emerging issues in the practice of University Learning and Teaching*. G. O’Neill, S. Moore, B. McMullin (Eds). AISHE, 2005. Released under Creative Commons licence: Attribution-NonCommercial 2.0. Some rights reserved. <http://www.aishe.org/readings/2005-1/>
- Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, Shamseer L, Tetzlaff JM, Moher D. (2021). Updating guidance for reporting systematic reviews: development of the PRISMA 2020 statement. *Journal Clinical Epidemiology*, 134:103-112. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.02.003.
- Parmi, I.T. (2009). *Reflection of educational principles of Ki Hadjar Dewantara towards national integration: Historical and cultural approach* (a dissertation). Yogyakarta: State University of Yogyakarta. <https://sps.uny.ac.id/id/berita/ismu-tri-parmi-doktor-ke-41-pps-uny.html>
- Pittenger, A. L., Fierke, K. K., Kostka, S., & Jardine, P. J. (2016). Developing interprofessional facilitators and leaders: Utilization of advanced health profession students as interprofessional (IPE) facilitators. *Currents in Pharmacy Teaching and Learning*, 8(1), 52–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cptl.2015.09.004>
- Pittenger, A. L., Dimitropoulos, E., Foag, J., Bishop, D., Panizza, S., & Bishop, J. R. (2019). *Closing the Classroom Theory to Practice Gap by Simulating a Psychiatric Pharmacy Practice Experience*. 83(10). <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe7276>
- Prapanca, E. (1350). *Kakawin Desa Warnana*. Indonesian National Library. <http://www.spaetmittelalter.uni-hamburg.de/java-history/JavaNagara-Kertagama.html>
- Quoß M, Rüttermann S, Gerhardt-Szep S. (2017). Cross-year peer-assisted learning using the inverted ("flipped") classroom design: A pilot study in dentistry. *Zeitschrift für Evidenz, Fortbildung und Qualität im Gesundheitswesen*, 126:84-93. doi: 10.1016/j.zefq.2017.07.007.
- Rebitch, C. B., Fleming, V. H., Palmer, R., & Rong, H. (2019). *Evaluation of Video-enhanced Case-based Activities Guided by the Pharmacists' Patient Care Process*. 83(4). <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe6676>
- Remington, T. L., Bleske, B. E., Bartholomew, T., Dorsch, M. P., Guthrie, S. K., Klein, K. C., Tinggen, J. M., & Wells, T. D. (2017). *Qualitative Analysis of Student Perceptions Comparing Team-based Learning and Traditional Lecture in a Pharmacotherapeutics Course*. 81(3).
- Schneider, A. R., Stephens, L. A. M., Catalina, S., Marín, O., & Semenic, S. (2018). Nurse Education in Practice: Benefits and challenges of a nursing service-learning partnership with a community of internally-displaced persons in Colombia. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 33(August), 21–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2018.08.002>
- Sari, S.M., Suhoyo, Y., Mulyana, D., & Claramita, M. The interactional communication of feedback in clinical education: A focused ethnographic study in a hierarchical and collectivist culture. *Heliyon*, 6;9(3):e14263. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14263.
- Soemantri, D., Nurokhmani, H., Qomariyah, N., & Claramita, M. (2022). The Practice of Feedback in Health Professions Education in the Hierarchical and Collectivistic Culture: A Scoping Review. *Medical Science Educator*, 4;32(5):1219-1229. doi: 10.1007/s40670-022-01597-8.
- Sonne, S., Kjaer, C., Möller, S., & Bloksgaard, M. (2020). Implementing collaborative, active learning using peer instructions in pharmacology teaching increases students' learning and thereby exam performance. *European Journal of Pharmacology*, 867(March 2019), 172792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2019.172792>
- Stagg, D. L., & McCarthy, J. (2020). Service learning: A method of instruction for community health content in nursing curriculums. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing*, 15(1), 9–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teln.2019.07.005>
- Suhoyo, Y., Van Hell, E.A., Kerdijk, W., Emilia, O., Schonrock-Adema, J., Kuks, J.B., Cohen-Schotanus, J. (2017). Influence of feedback characteristics on perceived learning value of feedback in clerkships: does culture matter? *BMC Medical Education*, 17(69). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-017-0904-5>
- Tauchid, M., Soeratman, Sajoga, Lahade, R.S., Soendoro, & Surjomiharjo, A. *Articles by Ki Hadjar Dewantara - Book 1* (1st edition). Yogyakarta, Indonesia: Taman Siswa Pub; 1962a.

- Tauchid, M., Soeratman., Sajoga., Lahade, R.S., Soendoro., & Surjomiharjo, A. *The Culture - Book 2* (1st edition). Yogyakarta, Indonesia: Taman Siswa Pub; 1962b.
- Tsuchiya, K. (1975). The Taman Siswa Movement: Its early eight years and Javanese background. *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 1;6(2):164-77. doi: 10.1017/S0022463400017306
- Vos, S. S., Sabus, A., Seyfer, J., Umlah, L., Gross-advani, C., & Thompson-oster, J. (2018). *Using Continuing Professional Development to Create Meaningful Co-Curricular Learning Opportunities for all Student Pharmacists*. 82(4). <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe6270>
- WFME. World Federation in Medical Education. <https://wfme.org/standards/>
- Williamson, G. R., Kane, A., Plowright, H., Bunce, J., Clarke, D., & Jamison, C. (2020). Nurse Education in Practice 'Thinking like a nurse'. Changing the culture of nursing students ' clinical learning: Implementing collaborative learning in practice. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 43(January), 102742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102742>
- Wright, G. B. (2011). Student-centered learning in higher education. *International journal of teaching and learning in higher education*, 23(1), 92-97.
- Zanchetta, M., Schwind, J., Aksenchuk, K., Gorospe, F. F., & Santiago, L. (2013). Nurse Education Today An international internship on social development led by Canadian nursing students: Empowering learning. *Nurse Education Today*, 33(7), 757-764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2013.04.019>
- Zimmerman, T., Schmidt, L., Becker, J., Peterson, J., Nyland, R., & Surdick, R. (2014). Narrowing the Gap between Students and Instructors. *Transformative Dialogues Teaching and Learning Journal*, 7(1):1-18. <https://journals.psu.edu/td/article/view/1251>

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